

2nd Annual Global AI Conference 2026
Human + machine: clinician-led AI for tomorrow's healthcare

Poster

Rejecting AI Legal Personhood: Targeted No-Fault Compensation for AI-Attributable Harm in Clinical Practice

Reference list

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